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Deliverable 20.1

CONCEPT PAPER

For an integrated poverty and living conditions indicator system (IPOLIS) database

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April 2014

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of live or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1. Aim and scope

The aim of this paper is to provide a general conceptual framework, as well as to set up a structure for the Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS). The paper will also serve as the basis of the forthcoming methodological and data infrastructure reports on three age groups: children, youth and older people. These latter papers will aim at defining the detailed, indicator level structure of IPOLIS, as well as at providing all the necessary inputs (data, metadata, etc.) for both the database and the visualization tool.

The role of IPOLIS within the InGRID project

IPOLIS will be the core outcome of the work package on innovative tools and protocols for poverty and living conditions research of the InGRID project. Work package 20 is part of the ‘Poverty and living conditions’ pillar of the project and integrates the research activity within the pillar. IPOLIS fits within the frame defined by the overall objectives of the project in many respects.

- Material living conditions and poverty and social exclusion in particular (also as defined by the Europe 2020 strategy target), stays at the core of the integrated indicator system.
- IPOLIS is conceived to be an innovative tool by including interactive data visualization.
- It will allow not only researchers, but also the broader stakeholder community to follow the situation of most vulnerable groups.
- It builds mainly on the European Statistical System, while other data sources are also considered as inputs.

The aim of the work package is to build a platform to improve infrastructure for monitoring, analysing and evaluating the situation of the most vulnerable groups. Nine specific vulnerable groups in total are identified:

About InGRID

Referring to the increasingly challenging EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the objectives of the [InGRID](#) project are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘poverty and living conditions’ and ‘working conditions and vulnerability’ by improving the transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

InGRID is supported by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Programme.

The Innovative tools and protocols for poverty and living conditions research work package (WP20)

The work package is part of the 'Poverty and living conditions' pillar. Its objectives (among others) are:

- to synthesise and make accessible data and knowledge in a structured form that backs comparative research on social policies, improves infrastructure to reach vulnerable groups at risk of poverty;
- to organise indicators and research results in a theoretical frame, with the aim of avoiding bottlenecks and temptations to carry on purely data driven research on poverty and living conditions
- to carry on purely data driven research on poverty and living conditions.

Tasks to be carried out within the WP:

Task 20.1: Building an integrated poverty and living conditions indicator system (IPOLIS).

Task 20.2: Optimising the use of census microdata to analyse and monitor poverty and living conditions at the territorial level in Europe.

Task 20.3: Identifying priorities for future data collection.

Related deliverables:

D20.1 Conceptual report for IPOLIS.

D20.2 Complete IPOLIS data base for the vulnerable groups.

1. easy-to-reach groups: (a) children (0-17 years), (b) youth (15-30 years) and (c) older people (65+ years);
2. hard-to-identify groups: (d) migrants, (e) Roma, (f) travellers;
3. hard-to-reach groups: (g) institutionalised people, (h) undocumented immigrants and (i) homeless people.

The **integrated poverty and living conditions indicator system** (IPOLIS) will be produced for the easy-to-reach vulnerable groups: children, youth and older people. This restriction of the scope of IPOLIS is, however, subject to debate. The selection of these three vulnerable social groups, already performed in the project proposal phase, was supported by the following considerations:

- the risk of poverty and of social exclusion is higher than population average for children, young adults and older people in almost all countries, when examined by age (e.g. Eurostat 2010);
- age easily identifies groups both in administrative and survey type data collections, which is not the case with other attributes;
- important prior efforts to monitor poverty, living conditions, quality of life and well-being exist for these age groups, especially for children.

However, the flexible nature of the proposed structure and implementation plan of IPOLIS allows for the inclusion of other vulnerable groups (e.g. disabled persons, migrants), when they will be coherently identifiable in a large data infrastructure, and robust indicators will be ready for production.¹ For the hard-to-identify and hard-to-reach vulnerable groups protocols will be developed for the creation of a database in a later stage.

The IPOLIS is aimed to improve infrastructure for analysing and monitoring the situation of most vulnerable groups. It is conceived to serve as a resource for various user groups (researchers, policy makers at different levels, NGO experts, journalists, students, etc.) to

- monitor the situation of children, youth and elderly in the field of poverty, living conditions and quality of life;
- observe relationships between indicators and to detect cross-country patterns according to selected measures.

¹ This process within Eurostat is in a very advanced phase in the case of disabled people. For details, see Pascal Wolff's presentation at the Budapest workshop <http://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call3/programme-and-presentations>.

Basic dilemmas

i. Theory or data driven indicator system?

The paper sets up a theoretical framework for IPOLIS. However, for the purpose of this specific indicator database only a data driven indicator system is the viable way. Accordingly, the structure of the database and the indicator selection process will be conditioned by the availability of data.

European Statistical System (ESS) data (regular Eurostat coordinated surveys, European Quality of Life Survey - EQLS, Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement - SHARE) will gain priority in selecting specific indicators. Besides these data sources, we will rely on other survey data generally used by similar initiatives (e.g. European Social Survey – ESS, OECD Programme for International Student Assessment – PISA, Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children – HBSC, etc.). We also retain the possibility to recommend new indicators or to advise the development of new indicators, when major gaps are identified according to the followings:

- the data infrastructure exists, but the indicator is not developed (e.g. EU-SILC indicators broken down by youth age groups);
- the data infrastructure is under development (e.g. MYWEB);
- there is no data infrastructure at all (e.g. certain aspects of early childhood development).

ii. How will IPOLIS handle three different age groups within a single frame?

With very few exceptions, prior indicator system initiatives relate either to one specific age group (e.g. children, older people, etc.) or to the population as a whole. The challenge we face this time is to develop an indicator system structure, which is able to handle three different age groups within a single frame. Therefore, in designing and building IPOLIS and the related database, we have to

- ensure a coherence of the indicator system structure at the level of domains, components and subcomponents;
- set up direct linkages between groups at indicator level that allow for a comparative assessment of their relative position – primarily according to the dimensions of poverty and material living conditions;
- consider that each stage of life cycle has its own characteristics and thus we need to pay special attention to age-group specific problems.

Figure 1 shows in a simplified way how the linkages between age groups can be established. Each portfolio of indicators belonging to an age-specific vulnerable group is represented in the figure by a differently coloured vertical rectangle. A set of indicators, referred here to as *overarching* indicators, characterizes all three groups. These measures should have the same definition and preferably should be produced on the same data source. The application of these criteria is facilitated by the fact that vulnerable groups in IPOLIS are defined by age. Household level indicators, like household income and material living conditions, meet these criteria. On the contrary, perceived general health or physical activity could also be relevant indicators for all three age groups, but there is no single data source to produce them.

In addition, some of the potential indicators can be relevant for not only one, but two vulnerable groups. For example, this is the case with risk behaviour indicators, which are relevant for both children and youth, or with employment rate which is an important indicator for both youth and older people.

Figure 1. Linkages between age groups

iii. Country and time period coverage of IPOLIS

Being a strongly data driven database, we need to clearly define its main parameters.

Country coverage: EU-28. The inclusion of Iceland, Norway and Switzerland in the database may be considered. These countries are part of the Eurostat Statistical System, with regular and EU compatible data collection standards. Some practical considerations also support this choice: it is easier to develop a larger frame from the beginning of the project than in a later phase, when the indicator database has already been set up.

Time period: 2004 (major EU enlargement) – 2012 (or latest year available at the time of data upload in the database).

iv. Evaluation of country performance

One of the main aims of developing and maintaining multidimensional and cross-country comparative indicator systems is to assess a country’s performance relative to the performance of others. There are different ways to provide a comparative evaluation of a country’s performance based on such an indicator system. One method is to compile individual indicators of a multidimensional indicator system into a composite indicator. An example for this practice is the child well-being monitoring initiative of the UNICEF. The UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (and similarly, the Report Card 11) provides a comprehensive assessment of the lives and well-being of children and young people in 21 nations of the industrialized world (UNICEF (2007: 2)). The league table presented compares countries by using a mixed

method: countries are ranked within dimensions of well-being (Material well-being, Health and safety, etc.) and these ranks are summarised in a single average ranking position. A similar method is at the base of the OECD Better Life Index initiative as well. Besides monitoring, this method serves advocacy objectives by stimulating the discussion and development of policies.

Another way to compare country performances relies exclusively on the individual measures of the indicators system, even though these measures might be composites of other elementary information (e.g. the material deprivation indicator applied by the EU social inclusion monitoring framework). This practice is followed by all EU initiatives, as well as by other initiatives, like the OECD Doing Better for Children (OECD 2009) or TÁRKI (2011). Often, besides the indicator by indicator evaluation of a country's performance (using time and geographical benchmarks), analytical frameworks are elaborated to provide condensed information in a multidimensional framework. A good example for this kind of analytical framework was presented in the EU Task-Force on Child Poverty and Child Well-being report (Social Protection Committee 2008), and taken further by the TÁRKI-Applica (2010) and the TÁRKI (2011) reports.

a multi-dimensional concept comprising objective measures, and people’s perceptions of these factors (economic, social, etc.), that is, subjective measures of objective substances (p. 17). The QoL concept we propose here includes objective living conditions (including material and non-material aspects such as income, material deprivation, quality of housing, education, health, etc.), and subjective perceptions about these factors (e.g. subjective income position, self-reported health status). Subjective measures are thus expected to be used here only with the purpose of better describing objective substances. (In practice this means that our intent is to leave open the possibility of using subjective indicators if they complement objective measures.)

It is to be highlighted that the proposed concept of QoL and thus the indicator system does not include such measures of subjective well-being like self-reported happiness, overall life satisfaction, etc. (This is to say that do not intend to capture subjective substance⁴.) This is, therefore, a major point of difference between the proposed indicator system and most of the well-being indicator systems (i.e. they usually incorporate indicators for self-reported happiness, life satisfaction, etc.). Actually, what we measure is the likely explanatory factors of people’s well-being rather than well-being itself (see Rojas 2011).

Figure 2 shows the conceptual framework set up for IPOLIS: the integrated indicator system builds on the quality of life concept, which includes the original concept of poverty and living conditions, but does not fully cover what we understand as well-being. In terms of indicator selection, IPOLIS will include objective measures as well as subjective indicators of objective circumstances, but indicators of subjective well-being, referring intrinsically to subjective phenomena will be excluded.

Figure 2. Conceptual framework of IPOLIS

Note: In the rectangles we indicated what outcomes/indicators to be added to shift from the given circle to the next one.

4 For the distinction between subjective and objective indicators see Eurostat (2010).

2.2 The general and age group-specific policy contexts of monitoring quality of life and well-being within the EU

2.2.1 General policy context

2008: The European Commission's Renewed Social Agenda explicitly seeks to enhance European citizens' well-being and quality of life through a broad range of measures. The priority areas for action are as follows:

- Children and youth
- More and better jobs and the enhancement of skills
- Mobility
- Improving the quality of life and the inclusion of the elderly
- The fight against poverty and social exclusion
- The fight against discrimination
- The promotion of social rights at worldwide level.

2009: The European Commission's 'The GDP and beyond' Communication⁵ was published following the Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission's (SSFC) report launched in the same year.

2010: The Europe 2020 Strategy on Smart, Sustainable and Inclusive Growth set an explicit poverty and social exclusion target to be reached by the end of this decade. The target was set up in a broad way: it defines the population at-risk of poverty and social exclusion suggests that the whole process aims to cover not only the income aspects of poverty, but also to reflect its multidimensional nature. The complexity of poverty and social exclusion are equally acknowledged by additional policy agenda's and initiatives, such as the 'Active inclusion' agenda, the Open Method of Coordination on Social Protection and Social Inclusion (Social OMC), the European Platform Against Poverty and Social Exclusion (EPAP).⁶

The EU-level evidence-based policy process which includes monitoring and target setting within the frame of the Social OMC has already started for several vulnerable groups, including migrants (New European Agenda on Integration of non-EU nationals⁷) and Roma (EU framework for national Roma integration strategies 2011⁸). Hereinafter, we present the evolution of the policy agenda for three vulnerable age groups: children, youth and older people.

2.2.2 2.2.2 Children: The evolution of child mainstreaming process within the EU

1989: The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was adopted by the UN. The UN CRC incorporates a full range of rights for children.

2005:

- The March 2005 EU Presidency Conclusions, which explicitly referred to child poverty and announced the European Youth Pact.
- The Luxembourg Presidency initiative on 'Taking Forward the EU Social Inclusion Process', which called explicitly for the mainstreaming of children and for the adoption of at least one child well-being indicator at the EU level.

⁵ http://www.growthintransition.eu/wp-content/uploads/beyond_gdp.pdf

⁶ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=961>

⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/news/intro/news_intro_en.htm#20110720

⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/justice/policies/discrimination/docs/com_2011_173_en.pdf

2006:

- The 2006 March Presidency Conclusions, which called for more action to eradicate child poverty in the Member States.
- The adoption of the Commission's communication entitled 'Towards an EU Strategy on the Rights of the Child, Communication from the Commission'.
- The streamlining of the Social OMC, since when there has been a more systematic consideration of several well-being indicators for children. The child well-being slot is not filled in yet, according to the 2009 review of the Social OMC indicator portfolio.

2007: The establishment of the EU Task-Force on Child Poverty and Child Well-Being.

2008:

- The formal adoption in January of the report and recommendations of the Social Protection Committee (2008) report⁹ by all Member States and the Commission, and the incorporation of these into the EU acquis in this area.
- The inclusion in National Strategy Reports of child poverty as a key priority in 24 Member States, many of which set specific targets for its reduction.

2009: The TÁRKI-Applica report, which was presented to the Commission and to the Indicators Sub-Group of the Social Protection Committee and published in 2010¹⁰.

2010: The Belgian Presidency conference on child poverty and the book on the roadmap for Europe 2020 of Frazer, Marlier and Nicaise (2010) commissioned by the presidency, which set out a 'roadmap' for recommendations to fight child poverty¹¹.

2011: The Hungarian EU Presidency, which submitted a Council Conclusion entitled 'Tackling child poverty and promoting child well-being' to the Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs Council (EPSCO) on 17 June for adoption.

2012:

- The SPC Advisory Report (Social Protection Committee 2012) to the European Commission on tackling and preventing child poverty, promoting child well-being.
- The Cyprus High Level Presidency Conference on Investing in children: Preventing and tackling child poverty and social exclusion, promoting children's well-being on 18-19 October 2012 in Lefkosia (Nicosia, Cyprus).

2013: The European Commission launched the Social Investment package (European Commission 2013a), including the recommendation of investing in children, adopted later on by EPSCO (Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs) Council of Member States.

In addition, a series of reports and calls of EPSCO Council of Members States in favour of tackling child poverty and social exclusion, were produced within the framework of initiatives funded under the PROGRESS stream, as part of the Social OMC. These included reports by the EU Network of Independent Experts on Social Inclusion, the European poverty networks (e.g. Eurochild, the European Anti-Poverty Network - EAPN, the European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless - FEANTSA and the European Social Network - ESN), various peer reviews and other exchange projects.

⁹ ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=2049&langId=en

¹⁰ <http://www.tarki.hu/en/research/childpoverty/>

¹¹ http://www.mi-is.be/sites/default/files/doc/EN-Report%20child%20poverty_BAT.pdf

2.2.3 Youth: The evolution of EU youth policy

2001: The White Paper on Youth (European Commission 2001) was adopted. It contained a proposal to increase cooperation in four youth priority areas: participation, information, voluntary activities and a greater understanding and knowledge of youth. It also proposed that the youth dimension should be taken into account more when developing policies in other related fields (including education and training, employment and social inclusion, health and anti-discrimination). Further, to improve participation, information, voluntary activities and knowledge of youth issues, the Council adopted 14 common objectives in 2003 and 2004 (see Council Resolutions of 25.11.2003 and 15.11.2004).

2005: The adoption of the European Youth Pact: Commission Communication of 30 May 2005 on European policies concerning youth: Addressing the concerns of young people in Europe - implementing the European Youth Pact and promoting active citizenship (European Commission 2005). The Pact consisted of three strands: (i) employment, integration and social advancement; (ii) education, training and mobility; and (iii) reconciliation of family life and working life.

2009: The Council of Youth Ministers in the 27 Member States of the European Union adopted a resolution which puts into force a new EU Youth Strategy for 2010 - 2018. The new strategy is based on a proposal from the European Commission, as a Communication entitled "An EU Strategy for Youth - Investing and Empowering. A renewed open method of coordination to address youth challenges and opportunities" (European Commission 2009b). The resolution outlines the main goals for a long-term strategy for youth:

- creating more opportunities for young people in education and the labour market and
- promoting the active citizenship, social inclusion and solidarity of all young people.

The EU Youth Strategy identifies 8 fields of action in which initiatives should be taken:

- education and training
- employment and entrepreneurship
- health and well-being
- social inclusion
- culture and creativity
- youth participation
- volunteering
- youth and the world.

As part of the EU Youth Strategy, the Commission set up an expert group on youth indicators. The expert group was given the tasks of proposing a dashboard of indicators in the fields of education, employment, health and social inclusion; and of providing an overview of possible new indicators in core youth policy areas (see above). For the results of the work see the Commission Staff Working Document on EU indicators in the field of youth (European Commission 2011).

Europe 2020 focuses strongly on young people, with a headline target of reducing early school leaving and increasing tertiary attainment. Two other headline targets also share a clear youth dimension – to reduce the risk of poverty and to increase the share of the population in employment.

Furthermore, the flagship initiative entitled Youth on the Move promotes youth mobility, while young people are also included in An Agenda for New Skills and Jobs and A Platform against Poverty and Social Exclusion.

2012: The adoption of the 2012 Joint Report of the Council and the Commission on the implementation of the renewed framework for European cooperation in the youth field (2010-2018).

2013: A Council Recommendation was adopted on establishing a Youth Guarantee, in which the Council recommends that member states ensure that all young people under the age of 25 years receive a good-quality offer of employment, continued education, an apprenticeship or a traineeship within a period of 4 months of becoming unemployed or leaving formal education (Council Recommendation of 22 April 2013 on establishing a Youth Guarantee).

2.2.4 Older people: Active Ageing and its policy antecedents

1991: UN Principles for Older Persons¹² were adopted by the UN General Assembly. This encourages governments to incorporate the following principles into their national programs:

- Independence
- Participation
- Care
- Self-fulfilment
- Dignity.

2002: The Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing (MIPAA) and its Regional Implementation Strategy (RIS) were adopted at the United Nations Second World Assembly on Ageing held in Madrid in 2002 and subsequently, the General Assembly endorsed the Plan on December 2002.

2008: The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Working Group on Ageing was established as an intergovernmental body reporting to the UNECE Executive Committee. It facilitates and monitors implementation of the international policy framework on ageing as set out in the MIPAA and its RIS.

2008: The European Commission's Renewed Social Agenda set out 'Improving the quality of life and the inclusion of the elderly' as a priority area of action. Furthermore, the elderly was identified as one of the most disadvantage groups under the 'Fight against poverty and social exclusion' priority area of action.

2012: The EU designated 2012 as the European Year for Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations (EY2012)¹³. In this context, Guiding Principles for the EY2012 were elaborated by the Social Protection Committee and the Employment Committee. Each of the 19 guiding principles relates to one of the three dimensions of active ageing promoted during the European Year:

- employment,
- social participation, and
- independent living.

The Active Ageing Index (AAI) was developed in the context of EY2012 to assess the untapped potential of older people. The AAI is a product of a joint project undertaken by the European Commission DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion together with the UNECE and the European Centre for Social Welfare Policy and Research in Vienna. The index measures the extent to which older people can realize their full potential in terms of employment, participation in social and cultural life and independent living. It also measures the extent to which the environment they live in enables seniors to lead an active life¹⁴.

2012: The UNECE Ministerial Conference on Ageing "Ensuring a society for all ages: promoting quality of life and active ageing". The principal goal of the ministerial conference was to evaluate the first five-year implementation cycle of MIPAA and its RIS.

2.3 Prior efforts to monitor well-being

In this section, we overview the most important prior initiatives for measuring well-being, including efforts made

- within the EU,
- by international organizations and bodies, and
- at national level.

¹² <http://www.un.org/documents/ga/res/46/a46r091.htm>

¹³ The ex-post valuation of the EY2012 is not yet available.

¹⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=89&newsId=1837&furtherNews=yes>

Table 1 presents the milestones in the history of monitoring well-being according to age group. Based on the review of these measurement efforts, we can identify the following limitations and flaws in case of the three vulnerable groups.

Children:

- Rich antecedents at both national and international levels. Significant efforts in the EU, especially within the Social OMC.
- Most of the initiatives rely on the well-being concept.
- The existing indicator systems are strongly data driven, even when a theoretical frame is set up.
- Ongoing debate on the role of indicators based on children's self-reporting, including subjective well-being indicators.
- Large cross-country comparative infrastructure, but with important gaps, as recently highlighted by a report prepared Richardson (2013) on surveys of children. Among the flaws of this infrastructure we can notice here the followings:
 - o children under age of 9 are not (or are poorly) represented in (mostly school-based) surveys;
 - o there is an important lack of cross-country comparative longitudinal and/or cohort surveys;
 - o the level of data harmonization in cross-country surveys is not always satisfactory;
 - o important groups of children in need (migrant children, institutionalized children, street children, etc.) are completely missing from well-being focused data collections.

Youth:

- There are very few international initiatives for this age group as compared to children. Even national initiatives are rare.
- No much attention is paid on the youth in the Social OMC: While age breakdowns for children and older people are provided, no breakdown is produced for young adults. However, some youth specific indicators (e.g. NEETs) are included in the Social OMC.
- As part of the EU Youth Strategy dashboard set of indicators was developed by an expert group (see the Commission Staff Working Document On EU Indicators in the Field of Youth). However, the proposed indicator set is strongly data driven, theoretically less supported.
- Also, a joint report by the Council and the Commission entitled 'EU Youth Report' was issued in 2012.

Older people:

- Efforts are rare for this age group as compared to children; and almost exclusively made at national level.
- However, the Active Ageing Index project, a joint initiative by the UNECE and the European Commission stands out as an important exception.
- The Social OMC contains indicators for the elderly, both in terms of age breakdowns of indicators (e.g. at-risk-of-poverty rate for 65+) and in terms of old-age specific indicators (e.g. replacement ratio).

Table 1. National and cross-national indicator systems related to different age groups (including currently applied indicator systems as well as initiatives)

	Currently applied EU indicator systems	EU initiatives	Other (non-EU) cross-country indicator systems	National indicator systems
Children	Social OMC: Social Inclusion and Health Portfolios (2009 update)	Social Protection Committee Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling Child Poverty and WB (2012) ¹⁵	UNICEF reports on child well-being IRC 7 (2007) & IRC 11 (2013); Bradshaw and Richardson (2009) OECD Doing Better for Children (2009) TÁRKI (2011)	UK: Every Child Matters UK: Save the Children UK: The Children's Society - Good Childhood Index Wales: Children and Young People's Monitor Ireland: National Set of Child WB Indicators US: Child and Youth WB Index US: America's Children: Key National Indicators of WB Canada: The WB of Canada's Young Children Australia: A Picture of Australia's Children New Zealand: Children and Young People
Youth	Social OMC Social Inclusion Portfolio (age-specific indicators only, e.g. NEET; youth age group not available as breakdown for aggregate indicators) (2009 update)	On EU Indicators in the Field of Youth (2011)	ILO Key Indicators of the Labour Market	Australia: Young Australians: their health and well-being
Older people	Social OMC: Social Inclusion, Pensions and Health Portfolios (2009 update)	European Centre Vienna Active Ageing Index report (2013)	Stanford Center on Longevity and Population Reference Bureau: SCL/PRB Index of Well-Being in Older Populations	Wales: Older People's Well-being Monitor for Wales US: Older Americans: Key indicators of well-being Australia: Older Australia at a glance UK: Social Exclusion Unit (SEU) Reports on older people
Total population	Social OMC (2009 update)	Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission Report (2009) Eurostat 2009	OECD How's Life (2011)	UK: Opportunity for All (for the age groups separately; no one framework for the age groups)

¹⁵ The SPC (2012) report closely follows the recommendations of the preceding SPC (2008) report, as a result of the work of the EU Task-Force on Child Poverty and Child Well-being. The recommendations of the Task-Force were formally adopted by all Member States and the Commission in January 2008.

3. The proposed structure (domains and components) of IPOLIS

3.1 Domains and components of similar indicator systems

After reviewing the available well-being indicator systems, we decided to outline two in this section. They are comprehensive both in terms of dimensions of well-being and in terms of covering total population:

- the 2009 Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission report (SSFC report 2009), and
- the OECD How's Life (2011).

3.1.1 The Stiglitz–Sen-Fitoussi Commission report

The SSFC report (2009) on the Measurement of Economic Performance and Social Progress suggested new avenues for better measurement in the area of societal well-being (quality of life, including subjective well-being). The report defined eight key dimensions covering objective and subjective aspects of well-being to be taken into account. These dimensions include:

- Material living conditions (income, wealth and consumption)
- Health
- Education
- Productive and valued activities (including work)
- Governance and basic rights
- Leisure and social interactions (inclusion/exclusion)
- Natural and living environment
- Personal insecurity (including economic and physical insecurity)
- + Overall life satisfaction.

The SSFC report also considers that quality-of-life indicators in all the dimensions covered should assess inequalities in a comprehensive way.¹⁶

3.1.2 OECD How's Life

How's Life?, a Compendium of OECD Well-Being Indicators, and the interactive, web-based tool [Your Better Life Index](#) are essential parts of the OECD Better Life Initiative, launched in 2011.

The framework underpinning 'How's Life?' identifies three pillars for understanding and measuring people's well-being:

- material living conditions;
- quality of life; and

¹⁶ At EU level, the European Commission's communication to the Council on measuring progress in a changing world (European Commission 2009c) refers to the SSFC report (2009) and expresses that the "Commission closely monitors and in many cases contributes to these developments to ensure international comparability between indicators" (European Commission 2009c: 4). Related to this initiative, a task-force (Sponsorship Group on Measuring Progress, Well-being and Sustainable Development) of the Eurostat was set up, with the aim of analysing how the challenges put by the adoption of the SSFC report (2009) should be met by the European Statistical System. The consolidated report of the Sponsorship Group (Eurostat and INSEE 2011) has been adopted by the European Statistical System Committee in November 2011.

- sustainability.

In terms of its scope, the approach distinguishes between well-being today and well-being tomorrow. In terms of its focus, the framework:

- puts the emphasis on households and individuals, rather than on aggregate conditions for the economy since, there may be a discrepancy between the economy-wide economic situation and the well-being of households.
- concentrates on well-being outcomes, as opposed to well-being drivers measured by
- input or output indicators.
- looks at the distribution of well-being across individuals. In particular, How's Life? looks at disparities across age groups, gender, income or socio-economic background.
- considers both objective and subjective aspects of well-being.

In terms of current well-being, the approach considers the following 11 dimensions:

Under material living conditions:

- Income and wealth;
- Jobs and earnings; and
- Housing.

Under quality of life:

- Health status;
- Work and life balance;
- Education and skills;
- Civic engagement and governance;
- Social connections;
- Environmental quality;
- Personal security; and
- Subjective well-being.

3.2 Domains and components of the proposed indicator system

Quality of life is conceived, in this report, as a multidimensional concept, and this stage of the project requires decisions about how many and which dimensions of QoL to include. Table 2 presents our proposal for the structure (domains and components) of IPOLIS. As it can be seen, six domains (or dimensions) of QoL have been identified, including material living conditions, labour market attachment and work-life balance, education and training, health and risk behaviours, social connectedness and participation, physical environment and safety. Beyond these six domains, policy and context indicators have been added to the indicator set.

Table 2. Proposed structure of IPOLIS

	DOMAIN	COMPONENT
	QUALITY OF LIFE DOMAINS	
1.	Material living conditions	Income, expenditure, wealth Poverty Material deprivation Housing
2.	Labour market attachment and work-life balance	Labour market attachment Work-life balance
3.	Education and training	Access to and quality of education Educational achievement
4.	Health and risk behaviours	Health status Health behaviours Risk behaviours
5.	Social connectedness and participation	Family and peer relationships Participation
6.	Environmental quality and physical safety	Environmental quality Physical safety
	POLICY AND CONTEXT DOMAINS	
7.	Policy indicators	Adequacy and effectiveness of cash transfers, efficiency Availability and quality of services Public spending
8.	Context indicators	Economic performance Population structure Household structure and demographic behaviour Social inequalities

In the remaining part of the paper, we will use this structure (domains and components) for showing the differences from other indicator systems (Table 3) as well as for locating therein the currently used and proposed EU indicators (Table 5).

Table 3 presents the major differences between the proposed structure of IPOLIS and the prior initiatives reviewed above: the SSFC report and the OECD How's Life. Since IPOLIS covers three vulnerable age groups, it seems reasonable to draw comparisons between IPOLIS and the prior age-specific well-being indicators systems, too. Child well-being indicator systems seem to be an appropriate choice because they are more advanced than indicator systems for measuring the well-being of young or older people. We decided to compare IPOLIS to the first comprehensive child well-being indicator system outlined in the UNICEF Report Card 7. This work served as a basis for further major initiatives in the field of child well-being, like Bradshaw and Richardson (2009), OECD Doing Better for Children (2009) and the UNICEF Report Card 11 (2013). These latter attempts are not included in Table 3, due to a high degree of similarity in terms of domains that we use as a basis of comparison. The initiative by the European Commission presented in the SPC advisory Report (European Commission 2012) is also omitted from the table, because no domains were identified in the monitoring framework.

As it can be seen in the table, the first six of the eight domains of IPOLIS are largely the same as those covered in the SSFC Report and the OECD How's Life. However, there are some important dissimilarities.

- A major difference is the dimension of “health”, including both the components of health behaviours and risk behaviours, which is neglected in both the SSFC Report and the OECD How's Life. At the same time, “health” is a key dimension in the child well-being indicator systems outlined in the UNICEF Report Card 7 (and also in the succeeding ones, like OECD 2009, Bradshaw and Richardson 2009 and SPC 2012). The importance of health and risk behaviours is also great for the youth. Further, declining health can have a detrimental effect on older people's quality of life. Therefore, health is included as a separate domain in the proposed structure of IPOLIS.
- Another difference relates to the dimension of “governance”. “Governance and basic rights” and “Civic engagement and governance” are separate domains both in the SSFC Report and in the

OECD How's Life initiative, but with different contents. In the SSFC Report, the domain of "Governance and basic rights" consists of three components: i) trust in institutions, ii) satisfaction with public services, and iii) active citizenship. As we can see, this dimension contains heterogeneous components. Of these components active citizenship (voter turn-out) is also included in the OECD How's Life. Civic engagement or participation in society is an important element of social inclusion; therefore we opt for including it in the IPOLIS. Admittedly, satisfaction with public services may also affect quality of life, though it seems more appropriate to conceive it as a subjective assessment of the quality of public services and as such included among the policy indicators. Trust (as expectation) can also affect quality of life, but in a more indirect way. We suggest considering trust, at most, as a national level context indicator within IPOLIS.

- Another key difference between the proposed domains of IPOLIS and of the above indicator systems lies in the dimension of "subjective well-being" or "overall life satisfaction. This flows from the differing concepts of WB and QoL. Well-being indicator systems generally include the domain (or component) of "subjective well-being". This is also true of child well-being indicator systems (UNICEF 2007 and also in Bradshaw and Richardson 2009). We opt for not including life satisfaction as domain (or even as component) of QoL. The main reason for this is that the concept of QoL in our understanding contains subjective measures only if they refer to subjective assessment of objective factors. This criterion does not meet in case of overall life satisfaction, since it is a subjective measure per se. Also, there is an empirical reason to omit life satisfaction from the proposed indicator system. As it is argued in UNICEF 2013, subjective well-being overlaps with other dimensions of child well-being, and is therefore best considered as a separate measure in its own right (rather than as one component of an indicator system) (UNICEF 2013: 38).
- Finally, as opposed to prior initiatives, the proposed indicator system includes policy and context indicators as separate domains that are structurally distinguished from domains that include outcome indicators of QoL. Policy indicators serve to better understand the relationship between social processes and government interventions, and their development partly relies on inputs from activities within the Social Policy pillar of the InGRID project. Context indicators help better understanding outcomes. Their role is further detailed under sub-section 4.2.1.

Table 3. Domains and components of WB in the different initiatives, as compared to the proposed domains and components

	TOTAL POPULATION		CHILDREN
	SSFC report 2009	OECD How's Life 2011	UNICEF IRC 7 2007
MATERIAL LIVING CONDITIONS	yes Material living conditions	no (see Income and Wealth)	yes
Income, expenditure, wealth	no (only income inequality)	yes Income and Wealth (domain)	no
Poverty	yes	no	yes
Material deprivation	yes	no	yes
Housing	yes	yes	no
LABOUR MARKET ATTACHMENT AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE	yes Productive and valued activities	yes Jobs and Earnings; Work and Life	yes in the Material well-being domain
Labour market attachment	yes	yes	yes
Work-life balance	yes Quality of employment component in the Productive and valued activities domain	yes	no
EDUCATION AND TRAINING	yes	yes Education and Skills	yes Educational well-being
Access to and quality of education	yes	yes	yes
Educational achievement	yes	yes	yes
HEALTH AND RISK BEHAVIOURS	yes Health	yes Health Status	yes Health and safety; Behaviours and Risks
Health status	yes	yes	yes
Health behaviours	no	no	yes
Risk behaviours	no	no	yes
SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS AND PARTICIPATION	yes Leisure and social interactions	yes Social Connections; Civic Engagement and Governance	yes Family and peer relationships
Family and peer relationships	yes	yes	yes
Participation	yes Governance and basic rights	yes	no
ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY AND PHYSICAL SAFETY	yes Personal insecurity	yes Personal Security; Environmental Quality	yes Health and safety
Environmental quality	no	yes	no
Physical safety	yes	yes	yes (only deaths from accidents)
	Overall life satisfaction	Subjective Well-being	Subjective well-being (incl. health, school life and personal WB)

Note. The table does not cover all domains of the proposed indicator system ('Policy' and 'Context indicator' domains are omitted).

4. Criteria for the selection of indicators

4.1 General criteria for the selection of indicators

When building an indicator database, the indicator selection process should be interpreted from the point of view of the overall structure of the indicator system, as well as on the level of individual indicators.

What criteria should be applied for the whole system of indicators? When considering this issue, it is worth recalling the criteria applied within the Portfolio of indicators for the monitoring of the European strategy for social protection and social inclusion (European Commission, 2009a: 3). According to it, the Social OMC monitoring framework as a whole

- should be comprehensive and as much as possible cover all key dimensions in the common principles;
- should be balanced as much as possible across the different dimensions;
- should enable a synthetic and transparent assessment of a country's situation.

When setting up IPOLIS, this set of criteria should be complemented by a further criterion. Taking into account that IPOLIS is aimed to focus on three vulnerable age groups, the indicator system should be balanced across these age groups as well.

In the EU context, again, we recall the criteria applied within the frame of the Social OMC (European Commission, 2009a: 3)¹⁷. According to this document, an individual indicator should:

- capture the essence of the problem and have a clear and accepted normative interpretation;
- be robust and statistically validated;
- provide a sufficient level of cross-country comparability, as far as practicable with the use of internationally applied definitions and data-collection standards;
- be built on available underlying data, and be timely and susceptible to revision; and
- be responsive to policy interventions, but not subject to manipulation.

Among other initiatives, the revised note of the High Level Group Reflecting on Future Cohesion Policy (2011) sets the following criteria for indicator selection:

- reasonable: capturing the essence of an outcome according to a reasonable argument about which features of the outcome they can and cannot represent;
- normative: having a clear and accepted normative interpretation (i.e. there must be agreement that a movement in a particular direction or within a certain range is a favourable or an unfavourable result);
- robust: reliable, statistically and analytically validated, and, as far as practicable, complying with internationally recognised standards and methodologies;
- responsive to policy: linked in as direct way as possible and potentially affected by the policy actions for whose assessment they are used, while not being subject to manipulation;
- feasible: built, as far as practicable, on available underlying data, their measurement not imposing too large a burden on Member States, on enterprises, nor on the citizens (see Section 5);

¹⁷ The setting of these criteria goes back to the Social Protection Committee 2001 decisions endorsed at Laeken. For more details see Atkinson et al. (2002). For the first presentation of the streamlined OMC process, see: European Commission (2006), revised and adopted in 2009 by the Social Protection Committee (European Commission 2009).

- debatable: timely and openly available to a wide public, with room being built for public debate and for their own revision when needed and motivated.

The Eurostat and INSEE (2011) report on measuring progress, well-being and sustainable development claims that availability, feasibility and relevance should be the main criteria for indicator selection, while the potential pool may come from good practices and academic literature. In terms of data source, the report argues that when several sources exist for the same information, preference was given to the source that allows for the best identification of sub-populations and links at individual level across dimensions, and sub-dimensions. Where there is no suitable European Statistics System (ESS) source, data have been taken from non ESS sources (such as EQLS or the European Social Survey). However, the quality of these data should be further investigated from a "fit for purpose" perspective.

Table 4. General criteria for the selection of indicators: a comparison of existing practices

	Social OMC ¹⁸	High Level Group ¹⁹	Sponsorship Group on Measuring Progress... ²⁰	UNECE, Eurostat and OECD Task Force ²¹	UNICEF MODA study ²²
Capture the essence of the problem	X	X (reasonable)	X (relevance)		X (relevance)
Normative	X	X (normative)			
Theoretically conceptualized				X	
Robust and statistically validated	X	X (robust)			X (free from measurement bias)
Cross-country comparability	X	only implicitly			
Availability and timeliness of data	X	X (feasible)	X		
Responsive to policy interventions	X	X (responsive to policy)			
Debatable		X			
Commonalities with other ISs (as second choice)				X	
Feasibility			X		
Attribution to dimensions					X
Variance					X
Coverage					X
Scalability					X

The UNECE/Eurostat/OECD (2012) report²³ also sets the general criteria for selecting indicators. They give priority to indicators based on theoretical concepts that are most fitting to measure specific aspects of sustainable development. These are referred to as "ideal indicators". The indicators are derived by taking into account the measurement methods described in the academic literature, however not all of them are currently available in practice. The choice of indicators is primarily based on conceptual grounds. As a next step, the authors of the report take into account indicators based on the analysis of commonalities in

¹⁸ Social Protection Committee (2009).

¹⁹ High Level Group Reflecting on Future Cohesion Policy (2011).

²⁰ Eurostat and INSEE (2011).

²¹ UNECE/OECD/Eurostat (2012).

²² de Neubourg et al. (2012).

²³ http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/documents/sustainable_development/2012/Report_on_measuring_sustainable_development_Dec_2012_-_for_consultation.pdf

existing Sustainable Development Indicator (SDI) sets, as being indicators which are included in the majority of existing SDI sets.

4.2 Further dilemmas of the indicator selection process

4.2.1 What types of indicators should we prefer?

IPOLIS will preferably include outcome indicators of quality of life, completed by policy and context indicators.

Outcome indicators: measures of the quality of life, describing individual or family/household level performance or reporting on the resources an individual possesses either at individual or household level to achieve progress in another dimension. An outcome indicator is also characterised by motivating policy action. In the case of IPOLIS, outcome indicators can be based both on individual and household level data.

Policy indicators: indicate the effectiveness and/or efficiency of a given policy in place. There might be several aspects to be considered as reference for effectiveness or efficiency (distributional fairness, intergenerational fairness, etc.).

Context indicators: indicators aimed at describing either the national socio-economic context or the characteristics of the given age group relative to the overall population or relevant subpopulation.²⁴ Context indicators can help to evaluate outcomes. The examples below illustrate this.

i. Overall socio-economic context

Example: the Gini index, indicating the overall level of income social inequalities in a given society. Confronting this indicator with poverty or other outcome measures of social exclusion, can help explain processes that take place at the bottom end of income inequality in the light of overall inequality.

ii. Given age groups relative to the overall (or relevant) population

Example: at-risk-of-poverty rate (AROP) of people living in single parent households (outcome) vs. share of those living in single parent households within the total population (context): those living in single parent households may be at high risk of poverty, but if their share in the total population is low, the related problem is less serious.

4.2.2 Reflecting on inequalities

Looking at the indicators used by existing indicators systems, we can see that these are either central tendencies or inequality measures of outcomes (usually at the bottom of the distribution). The first type of indicators focuses on outcomes characterising the whole population or main subpopulations, while the second reflects on the distribution of these outcomes. In the case of children, the UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 9 (UNICEF 2010) strongly supports and applies measures of bottom-end inequality in an exclusive way.

²⁴ The European Commission (2009) document on the streamlined Social OMC portfolio of indicators and the Social Protection Committee (2012) advisory report on child poverty and well-being define context information in a similar way, as most relevant to better frame and understand the national context (European Commission 2009: 4; Social Protection Committee 2012: 63). Similarly, the Commission Staff Working Document on youth indicators also uses contextual indicators. Although the document does not provide a definition of this type of indicator, it includes measures similar to what we identified here as population structure indicators (European Commission 2011).

An equally important aspect of inequalities can be tackled by reflecting on the differences in outcomes according to the socio-economic status of individuals, parents or households. Breakdowns by variables, like attained level of education, intensity of labour market attachment, gender, household composition, type of settlement, migrant status or ethnicity, constitute the main determinants of these outcomes and therefore provide an important input for policy making.

4.2.3 Objective vs. subjective indicators

Existing well-being indicator systems aim to measure both objective and subjective aspects of people's well-being and thus use both objective and subjective indicators. However, these indicator systems differ in how subjective indicators are defined. Some of them (OECD 2009, UNICEF 2013, EU Social Protection Committee 2012) use the term 'subjective' referring to the subjective appreciation of objective conditions (e.g. subjective health status), while others (OECD 2011; Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission's report 2009; UNECE/Eurostat/OECD 2012; TÁRKI 2011) use it referring to intrinsically subjective phenomenon (e.g. overall life satisfaction, happiness) as well.

In line with the conceptual framework presented in Section 2, we prefer the concept of quality of life to well-being for IPOLIS. Quality of life is considered here to be a multi-dimensional concept comprising objective measures, and people's perceptions of these factors (economic, social, etc.). The QoL concept we propose here includes objective living conditions (including material and non-material aspects such as income, material deprivation, quality of housing, education, health, etc.), and subjective perceptions about these factors (e.g. subjective income position, self-reported health status). Subjective measures are expected to be used for IPOLIS only if (i) an objective measure is not available for a given topic (e.g. risk behavior) or (ii) the objective measures in themselves are not enough to capture the essence of the problem and subjective measures are needed to complement them (e.g. self-reported health status).

To sum up these considerations, IPOLIS will include objective measures as well as subjective indicators of objective circumstances, but indicators of subjective well-being, referring intrinsically to subjective phenomena will not be included, neither as part of one of the six quality of life domains, nor as a separate domain. However, subjective indicators, like perceptions towards inequalities, poverty and redistribution will be considered among policy and context indicators.

4.3 Vulnerable group specific challenges

When building the indicator system, we face some additional challenges specific to the different age groups. In what follows, we attempted to list the difficulties we have to cope with.

Children:

- The project proposal refers to children as those being aged 0-17. The age boundaries of childhood are clearly set in the existing practice of monitoring child poverty and child well-being: all major works in the field consider children as those aged 0 to 17 years inclusive, in line with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Children (UN 1989). However, there might be practical reasons for stepping over these boundaries in both upward and downward directions when a given indicator is selected. On the one hand, for example, early school leaving, for which the reference population is the 18-24 years old (TÁRKI 2011, Social Protection Committee 2012), or 'Youth NEET rate' with an age coverage of 15-19 years (OECD 2009) are part of several child well-being indicator systems or recommendations. On the other hand, OECD Doing Better for Children (OECD 2009) argues that it would be desirable to extend the definition of childhood to the period before birth.
- The concept of 'well-being' has a special meaning in case of (young) children. Child well-being refers to the present well-being of children in contrast to the concept of 'well-becoming' which focuses on the outcomes of childhood (outcomes at a future date). A recent perspective in monitoring child well-being highlights that childhood should be viewed as a stage of life in itself, not simply one among many stages of becoming an adult (Ben-Arieh 2006). When measuring and monitoring child well-being, therefore, not only children in their future status should be considered but also children as persons today.
- The measuring and monitoring of child well-being has grown dramatically since the beginning of the 2000s. Recent reports are more likely than earlier ones to incorporate the children's perspective (rather than the adults' perspective), and to include indicators beyond survival. Later reports are also more likely to focus on positive aspects of children's lives, and to focus on children's well-being (rather than well-becoming) (Ben-Arieh 2006).

Youth:

- Up to now, little efforts have been made to monitor the well-being of the youth.
- Even the definition of youth is problematic. Sociologists have long argued that the 'youth' is socially constructed rather than biologically determined (Williamson 2002). According to demographers, under pressure from economic (employability, unemployment, etc.) and socio-cultural factors, the nature of youth is changing. Young people arrive at the different stages of life later than did earlier generations, along pathways less linear than before (European Commission 2001:9; European Commission 2005:3).
- The EU Youth Strategy does not operate with an official definition for the specific period in life when a person is considered to be "young". This definition varies from one Member State to another and the age to consider differs with time and socio-economic development. The EU Youth Reports (e.g. from 2009 and 2011) define youth as those aged 15-29, the dashboard of youth indicators covers the age-range 15-30, while the 'Youth in Action' programme (as an instrument for implementing the EU Youth Strategy) targets young people between 13 and 30 (European Commission 2011:2).
- Either of these definitions were applied, there would be a considerable overlap between children and youth, raising the question of where to classify components like risk behaviour or indicators like early school leaving. Our paper leaves this question open at this stage.
- For some core youth policy areas identified by the EU Youth Strategy, including, most notably youth participation, there do not appear to be any commonly used definitions, and thus indicators used in these fields of action are not necessarily in line with the policy objectives (Ecorys 2011:32).
- Further, there appears to be some data gaps in the core youth policy areas, such as youth participation, volunteering, creativity and culture (Ecorys 2011:33).

Elderly:

- So far, only few initiatives have been made to monitor the well-being of older people.
- The project proposal refers to older people as those being aged 65 and over. This boundary coincides with the pension age limit of most of the member states. Looking at other existing indicator systems, we can register different lower boundaries for older people's age-based definition. The Active Ageing Index initiative (AAI - Eurocentre 2013) includes many indicators set for younger age groups: for example employment rate for people aged 55-59 and 60-64 or remaining life expectancy at age 55. While AAI has the process of ageing as a core concept, which clearly justifies the inclusion of younger cohort, the quality of life concept does not necessarily imply such a choice. However, quality of life in pension ages is strongly affected by outcomes (e.g. labour market participation, wealth accumulation or health status) in earlier stages of life-cycle.
- Given the increasing life expectancy, it must be taken into account that older people are already a heterogeneous population group and are increasingly becoming so (Eurofound 2010).

4.4 A starting point for the selection of indicators

In Table 5, we present the indicators currently used or recommended in the EU according to the proposed structure of IPOLIS. The existing and proposed EU level indicator systems include:

- Portfolio of Indicators for the Monitoring of the European Strategy for Social Protection and Social Inclusion (European Commission 2009a),
- SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (Social Protection Committee 2012),
- Commission Staff Working Document on EU indicators in the field of youth (European Commission 2011),
- Education and Training Monitor 2013,
- European Centre Vienna Active Ageing Index report (Eurocentre 2013).

As can be seen from the table, there are domains, components and sub-components of IPOLIS that are not covered or only partly covered by these EU level indicator systems.

- First and foremost, there are two domains in the proposed structure of IPOLIS that are either completely neglected or poorly represented in the existing and proposed EU indicator systems: 'Social connectedness' and 'Environmental quality and physical safety'. Indicators of social connectedness are present only in the Dashboard of Youth Indicators (which is only a proposal at this stage) and in the Active Ageing Index.
- Social connectedness, – notably family and peer relationships – is important from the point of view of quality of life. They are present in several international initiatives such as the OECD How' Life, SSFC report (2009) or UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (UNICEF 2007). Out of the three age groups, it is only the elderly for which indicators of family and peer relationships are included in any of the existing EU indicator systems.
- Environmental quality and physical safety are important dimensions of quality of life. These factors are present in the OECD How' Life initiative and in the SSFC report (2009), but not included in the EU level indicator systems. Although, indicators of both environmental quality (e.g. air pollution, noise) and physical safety (crime, violence and vandalism) could be produced based on the EU-SILC, none of them are included in any indicator systems.
- There is another field of quality of life that is only partly covered in the existing and recommended EU indicator sets: the domain of 'health and risk behaviours', and especially the components of 'health behaviours' and 'risk behaviours' thereof. One notable example is physical activity, an important aspect of health behaviour, which is covered in several indicator systems, such as the Social Protection Committee (2012) report, the UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (UNICEF

2007), the OECD Doing Better for Children (OECD 2009), or the TÁRKI report on child well-being (TÁRKI 2011), but almost completely neglected in the EU level indicator systems (included only in the Active Ageing Index). There are many gaps in the field of risk behaviours, too. While indicators of illicit drug use are present in a number of international indicator systems (UNICEF 2007, Bradshaw and Richardson 2009, TÁRKI 2011), they are not included in the EU level initiatives. The same applies to the indicators of teenage pregnancy and bullying. The former is covered in the UNICEF (2007), OECD (2009) Doing Better for Children, Bradshaw and Richardson 2009, and TÁRKI (2011), while the latter is in UNICEF (2007), OECD (2009), and Bradshaw and Richardson (2009). We suggest considering the inclusion of these indicators for the relevant age groups if they otherwise meet the indicator selection criteria.

- While 'work-life balance' is a separate domain in the OECD How' Life, it is not generally highlighted in the EU initiatives. The SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (SPC 2012) is an exception. It stresses the importance of promoting a working pattern and environment that enables employees to balance work and parenting roles. However, we argue that the problem of work-life balance is not only important in relation to child well-being, but also to the well-being of youth. Some events of adulthood transition or their timing (e.g. parental home leaving, own family formation, childbearing) are associated with the ability of combining work with family life.

Table 5. Summary table of the existing and proposed EU indicators (related to the three vulnerable age groups) presented according to the proposed structure of IPOLIS

	CHILDREN	YOUTH	ELDERLY
1. MATERIAL LIVING CONDITIONS			
<i>1.1 Income, expenditure, wealth</i>			
Income			Median relative income of elderly people (60+)(OMC PP, OP); Aggregate replacement ratio; median pension income relative to median earnings (OMC PP, OP); Relative median income (AAI)
Wealth			
<i>1.2 Poverty</i>			
Extent of poverty	At-risk-of-poverty rate (0-17) (OMC SIP, OP)	At-risk-of-poverty rate (18-24) (OMC SIP)	At-risk-of poverty rate (65+) (OMC SIP, OP); at risk of poverty rate of older people (65+) (OMC SIP) risk of poverty of pensioners (OMC PP); No poverty risk (AAI)
Depth of poverty	Relative median poverty risk gap (OMC SIP, OP)	OMC: not for age group 18-24	Relative median poverty risk gap (60+) (OMC SIP, OP)
Persistency of poverty	Persistent at-risk-of poverty rate (0-17) (OMC SIP)	OMC: not for age group 18-24	Persistent at-risk-of poverty rate (65+) (OMC SIP)
<i>1.3 Material deprivation²⁵</i>	Material deprivation rate (OMC SIP); Severe material deprivation rate (0-17) (SPC)	OMC: not for age group 18-24 ; Severe material deprivation rate (for young people compared to total pop), YI	Material deprivation rate (OMC SIP); No severe material deprivation (AAI)
<i>1.4 Housing</i>			
Overcrowding	Overcrowding (OMC SIP)	OMC: not for age group 18-24 ; not in YI	Overcrowding (OMC SIP)
Housing costs	Housing costs (0-17) (OMC SIP); Housing cost overburden (SPC)	OMC: not for age group 18-24	Housing costs (65+) (OMC SIP)

²⁵ There is an ongoing methodological work on material deprivation in general (see Gordon, Guio and Marlier 2012, Guio and Marlier 2013), and on persistent material deprivation in particular (see D'Amrosio 2013). Therefore, there is the opportunity to split this component (similarly to the income poverty component) in subcomponents of extent, depth and persistency of material deprivation when the indicator development process ends up with the adoption of indicators as part of Social OMC.

	CHILDREN	YOUTH	ELDERLY
Housing deprivation	Housing deprivation (SPC)		
2. LABOUR MARKET ATTACHMENT AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE			
<i>2.1. Labour market attachment</i>			
Employment		Employment rate of the recent graduates (ETM)	Employment rate of older workers (55-59; 60-64) (OMC OP); Employment rate (55-64, 65-69) (OMC PP); Employment rate (55-59, 60-64, 65-69, 70-74) (AAI); Effective labour market exit age (OMC PP)
Precarious employment		Young employees with a temporary contract (YI)	
Self-employment		Self-employed youth (YI)	
Unemployment	Young people not in employment, education or training (15-19) (SPC)	Youth unemployment rate; long-term youth unemployment rate (YI); Youth unemployment ratio (YI); Young people not in employment, education or training (15-19) (SPC)	
Labour market attachment of hhs	Share of children living in low work intensity hhs (SPC); share of children living in hhs with low/very low work intensity (YI); People living in jobless hhs (0-17) (OMC SIP, OP)	Share of young people living in hhs with very low work intensity (YI)	
<i>2.2. Work-life balance</i>			
Work and leisure			

	CHILDREN	YOUTH	ELDERLY
Work and care	Share of children cared for (by formal arrangements other than the family) (SPC); Employees in part time (as % of total employment) due to child care (SPC: context indicator); Difference in pp between employment rate among people without and with children aged 0-6 (SPC: context indicator)		
3. EDUCATION AND TRAINING			
<i>3.1. Access to and quality of education</i>			
Early childhood education	Share of children in early childhood education (SPC, ETM)		
Educational attainment		Share of population (25-34) whose highest level of education is ISCED 0,1 or 2 (OMC SIP); Young people (20-24) having completed at least upper secondary education (YI); Share of population aged 30-34 with tertiary education attainment (YI; ETM);	Share of population (65+) whose highest level of education is ISCED 0,1 or 2 (OMC SIP); Educational attainment of older persons (AAI)
Lifelong learning			Lifelong learning (AAI)
<i>3.2. Educational achievement</i>			
Achievement in basic skills	Low reading literacy performance of pupils (aged 15) (OMC SIP) Low achievers in reading, maths, sciences (ETM)		
Early school leaving	Population aged 18-24 with at most lower secondary education not in further education or training (SPC)	Early school leavers not in education (18-24) (OMC SIP, OP; YI; ETM)	
4. HEALTH AND RISK BEHAVIOURS			
<i>4.1 Health status</i>			

	CHILDREN	YOUTH	ELDERLY
Objective health status	Low birth weight (OMC HP)(SPC); Infant mortality rate (OMC HP)(SPC); Life expectancy at birth, at 45, at 65 (OMC HP); Healthy life years at birth, at 45, at 65 (OMC HP, OP)		Remaining life expectancy at age 55 (AAI); Share of healthy life expectancy at age 55 (AAI)
Subjective health status		OMC: not for age group 18-24	Self-perceived general health (OMC HP); Self-perceived limitations in daily activities (65+)(OMC HP); Mental well-being (AAI)
4.2 Health behaviours			
Physical activity			Physical exercise (AAI)
Obesity		OMC HP: not for age group 18-24; Share of young people (18-24) with a BMI > 30 (SPC; YI)	Share of population with a BMI > 30 (65+) (OMC HP)
4.3 Risk behaviours			
Smoking	Regular smokers (15-24) (SPC: context ind.)	OMC: not for age group 18-24; Regular smokers (15-24) (YI)	Regular smokers (65+) (OMC HP)
Alcohol consumption		OMC: not for the age group 18-24; Alcohol use past 30 days (students turning age 16) (YI)	Alcohol consumption, number of litres (65+) (OMC HP)
Illicit drugs (cannabis)			
Teenage pregnancy			
Psychological distress	Young people (15-24) having had psychological distress during the past four weeks (SPC)	Young people (15-24) having had psychological distress during the past four weeks (YI)	
Suicide	Death caused by suicide (15-24) (SPC: context indicator)	Death caused by suicide (15-24) (SPC, YI)	

	CHILDREN	YOUTH	ELDERLY
Bullying (+ fighting)			
5. SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS AND PARTICIPATION			
<i>5.1 Family and peer relationships</i>			Care to children and grandchildren (AAI); Care to older adults (AAI); Social connectedness (AAI)
<i>5.2 Participation</i>			
Voting/Voter turnout		Participation of young people (18-30) in local, regional, national or European parliamentary elections (YI)	Political participation (AAI)
Volunteering		Young people's engagement in voluntary activities (15-30) (YI)	Voluntary activities (AAI)
Group membership		Participation of young people in political organizations/party or community/environmentally oriented organizations (15-30) (YI)	
Internet use		Young people using internet for accessing or posting opinions on websites for discussing civic and political issues (16-24) (YI)	Use of ICT (AAI)
6. ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY AND PHYSICAL SAFETY			
<i>6.1 Environmental quality</i>			
Outside air pollution			
Noise			
<i>6.2 Physical safety</i>			Physical safety (AAI)
7. POLICY INDICATORS			
<i>7.1 Adequacy and effectiveness of cash transfers</i>			
Adequacy of transfers			
PRE of cash transfers	Impact of social transfers in reducing child poverty (SPC)		

	CHILDREN	YOUTH	ELDERLY
Counterfactual (EUROMOD) indicators			
7.2 Availability and quality of services			
Early childhood education and care, child welfare and protection			
Health care		OMC: not for the age group 18-24; self-reported unmet need for medical care for young people compared to total population (YI)	Self-reported unmet need for medical care (65+) (OMC HP, OP); Access to health services (AAI)
Social services			
7.3 Public spending			
8. CONTEXT INDICATORS			
Population structure indicators		Ratio of young people in the total population (YI)	
Home leaving		Mean age of young people leaving the parental household (YI)	
Household structure			
Inequality			

Abbreviations

OMC – Portfolio of Indicators for the Monitoring of the European Strategy for Social Protection and Social Inclusion (2009)

OP - Overarching Portfolio

SIP – Social Inclusion Portfolio

PP - Pensions Portfolio

HP - Health Portfolio

ETM – Education and Training Monitor 2013

YI - Commission Staff Working Document on EU indicators in the field of youth (2011)

SPC - SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (2012)

AAI – European Centre Vienna Active Ageing Index report (2013)

5. Data infrastructure

In this chapter we take an inventory of data sources that may serve as an infrastructure for building and sustaining IPOLIS. We consider cross-country comparative surveys that are conducted on samples representing the total population or certain relevant segments of it (adults, children youth, and elderly). Obviously, we prefer datasets that span long time periods and thus provide the opportunity to analyse trends.

The wide set of indicators that constitutes the monitoring framework of the social OMC can be a starting point of building IPOLIS. The different indicator portfolios of Social OMC are based on solid, flexible and standardised data infrastructure. However, there is an increasing need to improve the 'Poverty and living conditions' research infrastructure in order to keep-up with the progress that takes place in the policy arena.

Table 6 provides an overview of the relevant data sources of which we have knowledge. The table shows the main parameters of the datasets, including whether the dataset is part of the European Statistical System (ESS) or not, which is a relevant issue, considering the sustainability of IPOLIS.

The status of the data infrastructure presented in Table 6, can be summarised as follows.

- Surveys and data collections²⁶ that are representative for either the total or the adult population are numerous and cover several quality of life domains and components that constitute IPOLIS. However, there are considerable differences in how these domains and components can be filled up with adequate indicators based on this data infrastructure.
- Most of these data collections are part of the ESS, however, their status varies largely in terms of the starting year and periodicity. For example, the EU-SILC and EU-LFS are conducted on a yearly basis at least and cover the whole post-enlargement period. This means that the domains of material living conditions and labour market attachment can be adequately covered in IPOLIS. In addition, the EU-SILC can provide important indicators for some other domains, like health or environmental quality and physical safety.
- In the case of surveys other than EU-SILC and EU-LFS, either the periodicity of the data is not suitable for a year-to-year monitoring of trends (EHIS, AES) or the concept and the design of the survey are restrictive from the point of view of IPOLIS (Eurobarometer).
- Some surveys (like PIAAC and Generations and Gender Survey for adults, as well as all children surveys but the PISA) that are not part of the European Statistical System, are weak in country coverage. Not only countries are missing, but in a few cases, countries are represented by only one or more regions, which implies an obvious restriction in the comparability of the results.
- Some specific domains of children's quality of life are well covered by a set of surveys. Foremost, education and risk behaviour should be mentioned here. Administrative data for young children's health status are also abundant.
- There is no specific data collection on youth, which would meet the requirements for IPOLIS. In addition, while many surveys being part of the ESS, cover the youth population, regular indicators produced on the basis of them, do not refer to the 18-29 age. The youth covered by

²⁶ The European Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) is basically a survey-based data collection, but there is an increasing number of countries where survey data are combined with administrative data from registers. For the sake of simplicity, we treat in this paper EU-SILC as a survey, but the reader should be aware of this important development within the European Statistical System.

the total population (or adult) surveys, but adequate age breakdowns are not always available in statistical reporting.

- The data infrastructure situation for the elderly is similar to that for the youth (i.e. the age-group is covered by surveys representing the adult population), with two major exceptions. First, in most of the cases, age breakdowns for older people are part of the current indicator publication protocol. Second, there is a data collection targeted to them: the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement (SHARE) is conducted exclusively among older people aged 50 and over. This is part of the European Statistical system, although the country coverage is not yet full.

Table 6. An overview of potential data sources for IPOLIS

Data source	ESS status	Age coverage	Time period, periodicity	Country coverage	Domains covered
Overall					
EU-SILC Statistics on Income and Living Conditions	X	Total population living in private households	2003-, yearly	EU-28, Iceland, Norway	Income, poverty, social exclusion and living conditions
Adult population					
EU-LFS Labour Force Survey	X	15 and over in private households	1983-, yearly	EU-27 (Croatia from 2012), Iceland, Norway and Switzerland	Labour market
EQLS European Quality of Life Survey		16 and over in private households	2003-, every four years	EU-28, Norway	Employment, income, education, housing, family, health, work-life balance, life satisfaction and perceived quality of society
ESS European Social Survey		15 and over in private households	2001-, biannually	Varies, EU-28 excepting Croatia, Latvia, Romania in 2012	Attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns
EHIS European Health Interview Survey	X	15 and over in private households	First wave: 2006-2009, second in 2014	First wave: EU-17	Height and weight, self-perceived health, reduced activities due to health problems, long-standing illness, smoking behaviour, alcohol consumption
AES Adult Education Survey	X	25-64	2007-, every four year First wave: 2007 (2005-2008) Second wave: 2011 (2011-2012)	29 countries (incl. Croatia, Norway, Switzerland)	Participation in education and training activities (formal, non-formal and informal learning)
PIAAC Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies		16+	First wave: 2013	24 countries in total, out of which 17 EU members, plus Norway (Flandres represents Netherlands, while England and N. Ireland represent UK)	Competencies in literacy, numeracy and problem-solving in technology-rich environment
HETUS Harmonised European Time Use Surveys		20-74	EU-wide data collection in 2000 (Spring)	15 European countries (14 EU MSs + Norway) in HETUS	

Data source	ESS status	Age coverage	Time period, periodicity	Country coverage	Domains covered
			Harmonisation guidelines also available for 2004 and 2009		
ICT Survey	X	16-74 (12-15 optional)	Yearly, first wave: 2008	EU Member States	Interaction with public administration, skills and digital literacy, e-business, e-commerce, security
Eurobarometer	X	18 and over	(Standard EB) 1973-, twice a year	EU member states	Various modules themes, opinion polls
Gender and Generation Survey		18-79	2000-, every 4-5 years (3+ waves)	19 countries in total, out of which 14 are EU-28 MSs, plus Norway	Fertility, partnership, the transition to adulthood, economic activity, care duties and attitudes
Children²⁷					
ESPAD European School Survey Project on Alcohol and Other Drugs		Children aged 15-16	1995-, every four years	39 countries in total in 2011, out of which 24 are EU-28 members, plus Iceland and Norway. Belgium was represented by Flanders, while Germany by 5 Bundesl..	Substance use
HBSC Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children		Children aged 11, 13, 15	1983-, every four years	43 countries and regions in total, with all EU-28 included except Cyprus. Belgium and the UK are represented by regions (French and Flemish part of Belgium, and England, Scotland and Wales, respectively). Iceland, Norway and Switzerland are also included.	Health and risk behaviours, family and peer relations, life satisfaction
ICCS International Civic and Citizenship Education Study		Children at their eighth grade (not younger than 13.5 years)	2008/2009	22 out of EU-28, plus Norway and Switzerland. Belgium is represented by Flanders, while UK by England	Conceptual understandings and competencies in civic and citizenship education.
PISA OECD Programme for International Student Assessment		Children aged 15	2000-, every three years	OECD countries, including all EU-28 but Cyprus.	Competencies in reading, mathematics and science

27 For an extensive overview and evaluation of international surveys of children see Richardson (2012).

Data source	ESS status	Age coverage	Time period, periodicity	Country coverage	Domains covered
TIMSS Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study		Children at their fourth and eighth grades	1995-, every four years	63 countries and regions, out of which 21 are EU-28 member states in 2011. Belgium is represented by Flanders, while UK by England and Northern Ireland. Norway is also included.	Competencies in mathematics and science
PIRLS Progress in International Reading Literacy Study		Children at their fourth grade	2001-, every fifth years	48 countries and regions, out of which 23 are EU-28 member states in 2011. Belgium is represented by Wallonia, while UK by England and Northern Ireland. Norway is also included.	Competencies in reading
Youth					
-					
Elderly					
SHARE Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement	X	50 and over	2004-, five waves so far	19 European countries, including Switzerland.	Health, socio-economics and social networks

6. IPOLIS implementation plan

6.1 The implementation plan

First, we recall here the aim and the main objectives of the IPOLIS. As already mentioned in Section 1, IPOLIS is aimed to improve infrastructure for monitoring and analysing the situation of most vulnerable groups. It is conceived to serve as a resource for various user groups (e.g. researchers, policy makers at different levels, NGO experts, journalists, students) to

- monitor the situation of children, the youth and the elderly in the field of poverty, living conditions and quality of life;
- observe relationships between indicators and to detect cross-country patterns according to selected measures.

In practice, IPOLIS is conceived

- as part of a stand-alone online platform of poverty research;
- as a source of data which can be easily accessed and explored by the users;

as an interactive interface, which presents the underlying data graphically, in a structured and a transparent way. In the previous sections, we presented the conceptual framework, the policy context and the proposed structure of IPOLIS. Hereinafter, we outline the implementation plan of IPOLIS.

Table 7. Implementation plan for IPOLIS

	Name	Status within the project	External deadline	Internal deadline	Type of activities	Note
1.	Concept paper	D20.1	March 2014	February 2014	Desk research	Responsible: András Gábos (TÁRKI)
2.	Methodological and data infrastructure report on children	MS88	July 2014	June 2014	Desk research, data collection	Responsible: András Gábos (TÁRKI)
3.	Methodological and data infrastructure report on youth	MS89	November 2014	October 2014	Desk research, data collection	Responsible: Olaf-Groh Samberg (U of Bremen)
4.	Methodological and data infrastructure report on older people	MS90	November 2014	October 2014	Desk research, data collection	Responsible: András Gábos (TÁRKI)
6.	Data visualization manual	-	January 2015	December 2014	Desk research, web design, programming	Responsible: Krisztián Pósch (TÁRKI)
5.	Report on policy and context indicators	-	June 2015	May 2015	Desk research, data collection	Responsible: András Gábos (TÁRKI)
7.	Data visualization tool – beta version	-	June 2015	April 2015	Web design, programming	Responsible: Krisztián Pósch (TÁRKI)
8.	Complete IPOLIS data base for the vulnerable groups	D20.2	January 2016	November 2015	-	Responsible: András Gábos (TÁRKI)

6.2 Methodological and data infrastructure reports

In the forthcoming period between March 2014 and July 2015, three methodological and data infrastructure reports will be prepared within the frame of Work package 20 that will directly feed in the IPOLIS database:

- MS88 Methodological and data infrastructure report on children;
- MS89 Methodological and data infrastructure report on the youth;
- MS90 Methodological and data infrastructure report on the elderly.

The methodological and data infrastructure reports mentioned here²⁸ are at the core of the IPOLIS implementation plan. They aim to

- provide a full indicator proposal for the given vulnerable social group (for children, youth and older people);
- prepare a database of the proposed indicators for all countries and all years specified by the present concept paper (including main indicators, as well as breakdowns and confidence intervals where relevant);
- prepare an indicator fiche for each and every proposed indicator.

The present concept paper, by setting up the IPOLIS structure and formulating the key aspects of indicator selection process, is also conceived to create a general framework for the preparation of the above listed deliverables. The proposed structure of IPOLIS was outlined in Table 2 and further detailed in Table 3. Criteria for building IPOLIS as a whole and for selecting individual indicators were described in Section 4.1. A separate chapter (Chapter 5) was dedicated to the overview of the existing data infrastructure.

When preparing the methodological and data infrastructure reports, we recommend that the authors consider or reflect on the following criteria or issues, as well.

1. Bearing in mind the general criteria for building IPOLIS (see Section 4.1), the number of proposed indicators should not exceed 50 (without breakdowns) for each age group, including all domains (from 1 to 6 according to Table 2) and components. The selection of indicators in domains 7 and 8 will be handled in a separate paper to be completed in cooperation with the authors of the vulnerable group specific methodological reports.
2. When selecting the individual indicators, one should keep in mind the set of criteria outlined in Section 4.1. One of these criteria refers to available and timely data. However, in some cases, it may happen that the data infrastructure exists, but the indicator is not reported on (or not yet fully developed) for a given vulnerable group relevant for IPOLIS (e.g. EU-SILC indicators broken down by youth age groups). The inclusion of such indicators should be considered in the same way as of 'recognised' indicators. When data gaps are identified, second best or experimental indicators can be proposed.
3. For each and every indicator, the use of breakdowns should be considered, when the available data infrastructure allows for it.
 - a. We strongly recommend that the following breakdowns be applied in each case where relevant:
 - i. sex;
 - ii. social background, (which is indispensable if we aim at reflecting on the differences in outcomes according to the socio-economic status of

²⁸ As part of the research activities within the poverty pillar of the InGRID project, three additional methodological and data infrastructure reports will be prepared: on Roma, on migrants and on hard-to-reach groups. These reports do not feed in the IPOLIS.

individuals, parents or households as discussed under 4.2.2) by using at least one of the followings:

1. relative income position: e.g. income quintiles or deciles, poverty status;
 2. educational attainment: e.g. highest attained level of education, years spent in education, parents' highest attained level of education for children and youth;
 3. or other factor allowed by the data source if the above mentioned variables are not available.
- b. If relevant, the following breakdowns should be also considered:
- i. age in those cases when age sub-groups represent markedly different stages of life cycle from the point of view of the indicator (e.g. young people's employment rates for those aged 18-24 and 25-29);
 - ii. household structure: number of household members, household type, number of parents or children – depending on the particularities of the data source;
 - iii. labour market position: e.g. employment status at individual level, work intensity at household level;
 - iv. migrant status.
4. Confidence intervals should be provided for each value of a given indicator, where the micro data are available.
 5. In addition to the existing literature, comments and suggestions provided by the participants of the Budapest workshop, which either directly relate to the selection of indicators or refer to important data gaps, should be taken into account, when preparing the reports.
 6. Inputs for the IPOLIS data visualization website should be provided, by preparing descriptions in a short and concise way (e.g. in a text box format). Further details related to this input will be agreed on between website developers and the authors in parallel with the advancement of the data visualization work.

We recall here the dilemma presented under 4.3, which refers to the clear delimitation of social vulnerable groups in IPOLIS by age. After reviewing the existing practices (among which that of the European Union is of first importance for us) and the specific aspects related to the main objectives of the IPOLIS, we suggest that **children** to be defined as individuals aged **0-17**, while the **youth** as individuals aged **15-29**. Considering the overlap between these suggested age groups, as well as other aspects that may be relevant during the selection of specific indicators either raised or not in the present concept paper, the authors of the related methodological report are flexible to deviate from this suggestion, in unison with the coordinators of the IPOLIS. In the case of **older people**, there different considerations are even more numerous. Where the age boundaries for older people within IPOLIS will be set, should be discussed and agreed at the beginning of the task between the authors of the MDIR for the elderly and the IPOLIS coordinators.

We propose the following common structure for milestones MS88-90.

1. Introduction: aim and scope, project context, IPOLIS short description and references to the concept paper
2. Policy context for indicator development and monitoring
3. Prior efforts to monitor quality of life and well-being

4. Measuring quality of life/well-being: specific issues, problems related to measurement and data infrastructure, identification of data gaps
5. Indicator proposal and breakdowns
6. Recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructure and the way forward

Annex:

- A1. Indicator database in an xls format, structured by domains, components and sub-components
- A2. Indicator fiches

The suggested length of a report is 30-40 pages, without annexes.

Annexes

The IPOLIS database will be built on the specific databases prepared for the three vulnerable groups. The database will be produced as an attachment to the methodological and data infrastructure reports. The databases shall take an xls format and include the following information:

- point estimates for each indicator, for all countries and all years available in the data infrastructure;
- confidence intervals for survey-based indicators, where microdata are available or data owners cooperate with the InGRID team and provide indicators based on the data infrastructure they possess. TÁRKI (together with the project coordinator) is responsible for contacting data owners when the availability of microdata is restricted for the public or when the need for specific expertise related to a given dataset arises.

The database shall meet the following requirements in terms of structure and layout.

- The structure of the database should closely follow the structure of the IPOLIS. One indicator should be represented by one worksheet, named according to the code of the indicator (see below).
- Indicator coding. Each indicator should be identified by a unique code, generated according to the following rule:
 - o Vulnerable group specification: C - children, Y- youth, E – older people
 - o Domain identified by its serial number
 - o Component identified by its serial number
 - o Indicator serial number
 - o Example (according to Table 6):
 - C1.2.1 At-risk-of-poverty rate after social transfers among children, as being part of the *Children* vulnerable group, of the *Material living conditions* domain and of the *Poverty* component and placed first within the latter.

The completion of the indicator fiche is of primary importance for IPOLIS. It does not only document the chosen indicator, but also serves as a unique source for the metadata linked to the given indicator within IPOLIS, and thus, provides elementary information for users. An indicator

fiche should include all the necessary information that allow the reader to understand and evaluate the values of the given indicator as presented in the database. Table 8 provides an example for such an indicator fiche.²⁹ A similar indicator fiche will be produced for the policy and context indicators, too. In the case of policy indicators, specifically when counterfactuals are suggested, a detailed methodological description should be provided in a separate row.

Table 8 Example of indicator fiche

Name		At-risk-of-poverty rate after social transfers among children
Definition		The share of children (aged 0 to 17) with an equalised disposable income below the risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equalised disposable income (after social transfers).
Data source		EU-SILC
Data owner		Eurostat
Data coverage	Time	From 2003 onwards, but different entry years by countries.
	Countries	EU Member States at the time of data collection
Data limitations		Different countries are missing from different waves the public UDB, but available for Eurostat (detailed information is needed here on each wave)
Statistical robustness		E.g.: Over time variance in certain countries requires further investigation of data quality.

²⁹ This indicator fiche example is based on the one used within the Study on Child Poverty project for the DG EMPL, coordinated by TARKI and Applica. For more information see <http://www.tarki.hu/en/research/childpoverty/index.html>

appendix 1 IPOLIS Data Visualization Website (Krisztián Pósch)

The IPOLIS (Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System) Data Visualization Website’s major goal is to provide an interactive online site which is able to serve the interests of researchers, policy makers, journalists, and all people who are intrigued by the substantive topic and methodology of the Indicator System. This summary reports on the actual status of the related work and introduces the major features of the website through a short guide of the menu system.

Figure A1.1 Website structure

The *main page* (or “*Home*”) is designed to present up-to-date information regarding the development and latest news of the project. The style will follow a regular newsfeed format.

General information includes all the relevant attributes of the program with a summary of the mission and an overview of the goals of it.

IPOLIS Database consists of detailed information on all three vulnerable groups (*Child, Youth, Older people*) while also adding a general introduction (*Introduction*) on their special status. Download

links will be available for registered users to access the databases gathered on each key populations separately or merged based on visitor interest.

Data Visualization contains the heart of the website with many interactive tools to overview the IPOLIS datasets.

- *Country Cards* establishes the opportunity to overview the trends of poverty on a country-by-country basis while also allowing registered users to download the relevant datasets.
- Under *Cross Country Comparison* visitors can request simple statistics in the subgroups and compare the standardized poverty indicators across countries.
- *Timelines* offers a different approach where the juxtaposition relies on time instead of countries. Here any and all of the countries' variables can be entered provided they can be plotted together.
- *Other visualizations on poverty*, the final part of this particular menu points to other existing data visualization initiatives where the enquirer can continue his/her pursue of the topic.

The **Tutorial** section is a novel part which was not included in the original pledge of TÁRKI. All tutorials will be designed in Prezi, which proposes an interactive online tool for swifter understanding of the methodologies and concepts employed by the project.

- General overview of the methodology covers the major methodological considerations behind the indicators and establishes the guidelines applied throughout the project.
- Understanding concepts and constructs grants insight to the theoretical and quantitative debates and developments through elaborating the underlying ideas and types of indicators.
- Understanding statistics describes the basic statistical notions implemented in the composition of the database.

Context depicts the other parts of the poverty pillar which are only loosely connected to the IPOLIS enterprise.

- Vulnerable groups is an introduction to other special groups which are not in the focus of the current investigation.
- Census based poverty maps presents the BARCELONA groups work on Optimising the use of census micro□ data to analyse and monitor poverty and living conditions at the territorial level in Europe.
- The Poverty Pillar is an overview of the aims, structure, and members of the InGRID project.

Contact us is a regular interface where visitors can get in touch with the administrator of the website and ask their questions or add their comments.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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Inclusive Growth Research
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